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SURVEY RESULTS OF THE FACTORS AFFECTING ORGANIC FOOD PURCHASE INTENTION OF CONSUMERS

Associate Professor, Ph.D. Hoang Thanh Tung

University of Labour and Social Affairs Email: hoangthanhtung15@gmail.com

Truong Tri Tai

Le Hong Phong High School for The Gifted Email: tritaitruong2006@gmail.com

Postgraduate. Nguyen Thi Huong

University of Labour and Social Affairs Email: nguyenhuongf@gmail.com

Corresponding author: hoangthanhtung15@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The research examines factors that influence the organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers. In accordance with theoretical behavioral models and organic food research, data was collected and analyzed via SMARTPLS. Inspecting results demonstrate that 4 factors have a positive influence on organic food purchase intention. Additionally, the research team evaluates the levels of influence of each factor through descriptive statistics of the factors' average value. The evaluating results are the foundation to propose remedies that encourage the organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers.

KEYWORDS

Levels of influence, purchase intention, organic food, Vietnamese consumers.

1. Literature overview and research model

Organic food is defined as food produced without herbicides, pesticides, antibiotics, inorganic manure, and growth hormones (Honkanen, Verplanken, & Olsen, 2006). Diversified sources define organic food differently, but most of them depend on properties, including safety, nutrition, degree of importance, and nature. (Kahl et al., 2012).

In Vietnam, organic food received standardized certification from legitimate organizations in the food market: USDA (USA), NASAA (Australia), and Control Union - an organization that assesses and licenses European Organic standards. Currently, the Vietnamese organic food market is developing considerably with the appearance of organic food stores or specific retail displays in supermarkets. The origin and development of the organic food market stem from the demand for a healthy diet of consumers.

TRA (Theory of Reasoned Action) - a research model from a psychosocial perspective to determine factors of conscious behavioral tendencies (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1975), including (i) *Consumers’ attitude to perform an act*; and (ii) *Consumers’ subjective norms*.

TPB (Theory of Planned Behaviors) - is built from the original theory TRA. Model TPB of Ajzen (1991) adds a factor “*Perceived behavior control*”, after two previous ones *Attitude* and *Subjective norms*, affecting the consumers’ behavior.

The conceptual model includes 8 independent variables: *Health consciousness (HC)*, *Environmental concern (EC)*, *Personal attitude (PA)*; *Subjective norms (SN)*; *Perceived behavior control (PBC)*; *Food price (FP)*; *Food availability (FA)*; *Transparent information (TI)* which affect the dependent variable “*Organic food purchase intention*” (OFPI).

The research team examines factors influencing organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers, conducting a survey, and analyzing 528 responses, and accreditation is implemented by SMARTPLS.

Eight factors are deployed for this research model. However, the results illustrate 4 factors have a positive influence on organic food purchase intention: the highest impact is recorded for Perceived behavior control (PBC) (0.267); the second highest is Transparent information (TI) (0.210); and two factors Subjective norms (SN) and Food availability (FA) have an identical impact (0.138).

Figure 1: Linear structural model analysis

Source: Inspecting results via SMARTPLS of research team

To attach additional inspecting results and propose remedies encouraging organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers, with the factors designed according to the Likert 5 scale, the research team implemented supplemental evaluation levels of influence of factors through descriptive statistics of the factors' average value.

Distance value = (Maximum - Minimum) / n = (5-1)/5 = 0.8

Factors' average value is statistically significant if in:

1.00 - 1.80: Strongly disagree.

1.81 - 2.60: Disagree.

2.61 - 3.40: Neutral.

3.41 - 4.20: Agree.

4.21 - 5.00: Strongly agree

Factors are considered under the results of quantitative analysis from the factor with the strongest impact to the factor with the least impact (*in agreement with the absolute value of the impact coefficient*). The results of analysis and evaluation are the basis for proposing solutions to promote the organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers.

2. Evaluating levels of influence of factors affecting organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers

Factor **“Perceived behavior control”** with impact coefficient in the linear structural model reaching 0.267 demonstrates that when perceived behavior control increases by 1-unit, organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers rises by 0.267 units. The average value of this factor is 3.585. Observant variable **“I can afford organic food.”** (PBC1) reaches 3.636; observant variable **“I have some knowledge about organic food.”** (PBC2) reaches 3.616; observant variable **“I am ready to spend money on organic food.”** (PBC3) reaches 3.559; observant variable **“I can purchase organic food without difficulties.”** (PBC4)reaches 3.527. All the scales reach threshold **informants agree** with statements about perceived behavior control. Therefore, **it is vital to organize training sessions, discussions, and share production processes to provide knowledge and demonstrate resources for consumers.**

Figure 2: Factor “Perceived behavior control”

Source: Survey results of research team

Factor **“Transparent information”** with impact coefficient in the linear structural model reaching 0.210 demonstrates that when transparent information increases by 1-unit, organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers rises by 0.210 units. The average value of this factor is 3.647. Observant variable *“I pay attention to organic food’s labels or packaging.”* (TI1) reaches 3.669; observant variable *“I pay attention to organic food possessing qualified certification.”* (TI2) reaches 3.648; observant variable *“I pay attention to accurate information on organic food’s labels or packaging.”* (TI3) reaches 3.644; observant variable *“I have faith in organizations which license food quality currently.”* (TI4)reaches 3.625. Observant variables TI3 and TI4, after inspecting, are eliminated from the model because the outer loadings value <0.7. All the scales reach threshold **informants agree** with statements about transparent information. Therefore, **organic food should have a label, and stamp/logo from dependable organizations to create trust and promote purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers.**

Figure 3: Factor “Transparent information”

Source: Survey results of research team

Factor **“Subjective norms”** with impact coefficient in the linear structural model reaching 0.138 demonstrates that when subjective norms increase by 1-unit, organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers rises by 0.138 units. The average value of this factor is 3.589. Observant variable *“I pay attention to organic food’s labels or packaging.”* (SN1) reaches 3.642; observant variable *“I pay attention to organic food possessing qualified certification.”* (SN2) reaches 3.566; observant variable *“I pay attention to accurate information on organic food’s labels or packaging.”* (SN3) reaches 3.629; observant variable *“I have faith in organizations which license food quality currently.”* (SN4)reaches 3.517. Observant variable SN3, after inspecting, is eliminated from the model because the outer loadings value <0.7. All the scales reach threshold **informants agree** with statements about subjective norms. In other words, **when families and friends are more inclined to purchase organic food; magazines, and online networking sites promote organic food, consumers will have more tendency to utilize it.**

Figure 4: Factor “Subjective norms”

Source: Survey results of research team

Factor **“Food availability”** with impact coefficient in the linear structural model reaching 0.138 demonstrates that when food availability increases by 1-unit, organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers rises by 0.138 units. The average value of this factor is 3.607. Observant variable *“I can find organic food in my local area.”* (FA1) reaches 3.576; observant variable *“I can find organic food at supermarkets.”* (FA2) reaches 3.598; observant variable *“I can find organic food at green stores.”* (FA3) reaches 3.661; observant variable *“I can find organic food on social networking sites.”* (FA4)reaches 3.591. Observant variables FA3 and FA4, after inspecting, are eliminated from the model because the outer loadings value <0.7. All the scales reach threshold **informants agree** with statements about food availability. This means that **once the market develops, with the supporting policies of the government, private companies are allowed to invest money in producing organic food, creating opportunities for young entrepreneurs, and communities or groups.**

Figure 5: Factor “Food availability”
 Source: Survey results of research team

Factor **“Health consciousness”** with impact coefficient in the linear structural model reaching 0.037 demonstrates that when health consciousness increases by 1-unit, organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers rises by 0.037 units. Even though, after inspecting, this factor is statistically insignificant, the research team still considers statements of informants. The average value of this factor is 3.729. Observant variable *“I buy organic food due to its health benefits.”* (HC1) reaches 3.72; observant variable *“I buy organic food to ensure health safety for me and my family.”* (HC2) reaches 3.765; observant variable *“I pay attention to the long-term impact of consuming food.”* (HC3) reaches 3.777; observant variable *“I can sacrifice some eating interests to possess the best health.”* (HC4)reaches 3.652. All the scales reach threshold **informants agree** with statements about health consciousness. Therefore, **companies producing organic food should organize exchange sessions, discussions, and training so as to provide consumers with information about health benefits.**

Figure 6: Factor “Health consciousness”
 Source: Survey results of research team

Factor **“Environmental concern”** with impact coefficient in the linear structural model reaching 0.057 demonstrates that when environmental concern increases by 1 unit, organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers rises by 0.057 units. Even though, after inspecting, this factor is statistically insignificant, the research team still considers statements of informants. The average value of this factor is 3.664. Observant variable *“I buy organic food since it contributes to environmental protection.”* (EC1) reaches 3.771; observant variable *“I think organic food is environmentally friendly.”* (EC2) reaches 3.621; observant variable *“Present pollution influences my organic food purchase intention.”* (EC3) reaches 3.574; observant variable *“Production of organic food utilizes fewer chemical substances which are detrimental to the environment.”* (EC4)reaches 3.691. Observant variable EC4, after inspecting, is eliminated from the model because the outer loadings value <0.7. All the scales reach threshold **informants agree** with statements about environmental concern. In other words, this demonstrates that **while consumers acknowledge the environmental pollution of late via newspapers, magazines, online networking sites, e-WOM, and discussions, it is probable that they will have more tendency to purchase organic food.**

Figure 7: Factor “Environmental concern”
 Source: Survey results of research team

Factor **“Personal attitude”** with impact coefficient in the linear structural model reaching 0.087 demonstrates that when personal attitude increases by 1-unit, organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers rises by 0.087 units. Even though, after inspecting, this factor is statistically insignificant, the research team still considers statements of informants. The average value of this factor is 3.665. Observant variable *“I believe organic food has less chemical substance than traditionally grown one.”* (PA1) reaches 3.739; observant variable *“I believe organic food has a better taste than traditionally grown one.”* (PA2) reaches 3.581; observant variable *“I believe organic food has a better quality than traditionally grown one.”* (PA3) reaches 3.691; observant variable *“I believe organic food is safer than traditionally grown one.”* (PA4)reaches 3.684; observant model *“I believe organic food is more visually attractive than traditionally grown one.”* (PA5) reaches 3.629. Observant variables PA4 and PA5, after inspecting, are eliminated from the model because the outer loadings value <0.7. All the scales reach threshold **informants agree** with statements about personal attitude. As a result, **government policies, authorities, firms, and corporations ought to administer campaigns that raise awareness, and transform into positive attitudes or perspectives about organic food among consumers.**

Figure 8: Factor “Personal attitudes”

Source: Survey results of research team

Factor **“Food price”** with impact coefficient in the linear structural model reaching 0.021 demonstrates that when food price increases by 1-unit, organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers rises by 0.021 units. Even though, after inspecting, this factor is statistically insignificant, the research team still considers statements of informants. The average value of this factor is 3.61. Observable variable *“I believe organic food has a higher price than traditionally grown ones.”* (FP1) reaches 3.703; observable variable *“I believe organic food’s price is suitable due to its quality.”* (FP2) reaches 3.589; observable variable *“I believe organic food’s price is suitable due to its production.”* (FP3) reaches 3.614; observable variable *“I believe organic food’s price is acceptable.”* (FP4) reaches 3.534. All the scales reach threshold **informants agree** with statements about food price. This statement ensures that **Vietnamese consumers are satisfied with the food price when considering merits, production process, food quality ... However, high prices also deter them from reaching consumers, so financial aid and discounts are required.**

Figure 9: Factor “Food price”

Source: Survey results of research team

Factor **“Organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers”** has an average value of 3.577. All the scales reach threshold **informants agree**. This illustrates that informants agree with statements: *“I choose organic food over traditionally grown ones.”* (OFPI1) reaches 3.557; *“I have a possibility to purchase organic food in the future.”* (OFPI2) reaches 3.536; *“I am ready to purchase organic food in the future.”* (OFPI3) reaches 3.6; *“I actively find organic food.”* (OFPI4) reaches 3.617; *“I will introduce organic food to my family and friends.”* (OFPI5) reaches 3.574.

Figure 10: Factor “Organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers”

Source: Survey results of research team

Via analyzing factors influencing organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers, informants almost agree with the statements in the survey. Following quantitative research results and evaluation of levels of influence, the research team put forward solutions to promote organic food purchase intention in the Vietnamese market.

3. Remedies promoting organic food purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers

3.1. Solutions from the government

- Marketing positively about the merits of organic food in daily lives so the consumers have access to information about the environment and families. Additionally, communities or cooperatives are formed and operated proactively. Consumers are more inclined to purchase when family members, friends, and neighbors motivate them.

- Organizing fund-raising campaigns, inspiring people to invest money in the market, and creating opportunities for young entrepreneurs, which will alleviate financial constraints for organic farms. Reducing financial struggles, firms will boost their productivity, enhancing the facilities and farming process.

- Supporting conventional farms acknowledging the potential of the organic food market and encouraging them to change. Therefore, the food supply becomes more diversified, meeting the high expectations of consumers.

- Innovating policies, improving mechanisms, effectively deploying strategies, developing synchronously, and creating opportunities for the expansion of the organic food market. Businesses enhance their farming methods and develop different kinds of products. Implementing the regulations strictly to promote the transition process sooner.

- Enhancing facilities, including farming methods, reducing the use of pesticide and chemical substances, drainage systems, and greenhouse systems for extreme weather, on a national or international basis. Depending on the characteristics of each area, weather, climate, and infrastructure are being innovated suitably to create the most optimal environment for the growth of organisms.

- Organizing training courses for manufacturing enterprises; consulting, supporting, and providing information; organizing seminars, conferences, and discussions; coordinating with local agencies and government organizations to promote the organic food market.

- Supporting consumers to access organic food through policies, incentive programs, and discounts. High prices are one of the main reasons affecting purchase intention. With acceptable

prices, consumers can access them; hence, the target customer becomes more varied and richer, partly improving the marketing aspect.

3.2. Remedies from firms producing and supplying organic food.

- Enterprises are required to acknowledge the benefits and potential growth of organic food; proposing and implementing campaigns, and solutions focusing on that market; investing in research and reality; and collaborating among national and international businesses.

- Utilizing advanced scientific scientific-technical achievements in storing food; and keeping data, statistics about designs, and origins. Transparent, accurate, and sufficient information builds trust in consumers. Managing databases maximizes the efficiency of regular recapitulations, evaluating products, and possessing a broad view of companies.

- Each company produces its operational systems, which are unique and suitable for external factors, including human resources, location, and geographical characteristics. Specialized operation means that target customers and marketing campaigns become more unique. A market with diverse organic food allows consumers a rich supply, fulfilling their requirements for fresh meals.

- Minimizing pesticides and chemical substances, maintaining the quality of organic food, and meeting consumers' expectations for health reasons. Furthermore, it also reduces the risk of spreading noxious substances to nearby farms.

- Building and enhancing the product ecosystem. Providing that communities, groups, and cooperatives share their experience, answer questions, or provide information, the ecosystem creates more trust in consumers. Developing the product ecosystem is in line with more varied supply; acceptable prices, supporting the Vietnamese consumers to access organic food; creating a trend and strong wave of transformation.

Transforming from conventional products to organic food requires support from the government and companies to promote the process and food quality. Each proposed solution ought to be considered and executed, depending on each company, or farm.

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